

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1930	Harold Bloom	1951	1955	2019		American literary critic and the Sterling Professor of Humanities at Yale University	1930-2019
1930	Eric Sunderland	1951		1997		British Welsh anthropologist and academic	1930-2007
1930	John Strugnell	1952	No	1991		British chief editor of the official Dead Sea Scroll editorial team	1930-2007
1930	Joan Metge	1952	1958	2004	w	New Zealander social anthropologist, educator, lecturer and writer	
1930	Marta Traba	1952		1983		Argentinian art critic and writer known for her contributions to Latin American art and literature	1930-1983
1930	Seth Benardete	1953	1955	1994		American classicist and philosopher	1930-2001
1930	Helmut Kirchmeyer	1954	No	1990		German musicologist, philologist and historian	
1930	Bernard Benstock	1954		1994		American literary critic and a professor of English	1930-1994
1930	Kenneth A. R. Kennedy	1954	1962	2005		American Professor Emeritus of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, Anthropology and Asian Studies in the Division of Biological Sciences at Cornell University	1930-2014
1930	Marshall Sahlins	1954	1954	1997		American anthropologist best known for his ethnographic work in the Pacific and for his contributions to anthropological theory	
1930	Ezra Vogel	1955	1958	2000		American Professor of the Social Sciences Emeritus	
1930	Dietz-Otto Edzard	1955	1955	1999		German scholar of the Ancient Near East and grammarian of the Sumerian language	1930-2004
1930	Ioan Lewis	1955	1957	1992		British Scottish professor emeritus of anthropology at the London School of Economics	1930-2014
1930	John MacInnes	1955		1993		British Scottish Gaelic scholar and authority on Scottish Gaelic oral tradition	1930-2019
1930	Валентина Майногашева	1956	1958		w	Russian philologist, folklorist, professor of the department of Khakass philology	
1930	Aina Moll Marquès	1956	No	1996	w	Spanish philologist and politician	1930-2019
1930	Stanford J. Shaw	1956	1958	1992		American historian, best known for his works on the late Ottoman Empire, Turkish Jews, and the early Turkish Republic	1930-2006
1930	Ernst Vogt	1956	1956	1999		German classical philologist	1930-2017

1930	Radoslav Katičić	1957	1959	1998	Croatian linguist, classical philologist, Indo-Europeanist, Slavist and Indologist	1930-2019
1930	László Antal	1957	1957	1993	Hungarian linguist, structuralist (lone wolf in Hungarian linguistics)	1930-1993
1930	Jacques Derrida	1957	1957	1998	Algerian-French philosopher best known for developing a form of semiotic analysis known as deconstruction, which he discussed in numerous texts, and developed in the context of phenomenology	1930-2004
1930	David R. Harris	1957	1963	1996	British geographer, anthropologist, archaeologist and academic, well known for his detailed work on the origins of agriculture and the domestication of plants and animals	1930-2013
1930	David McLintock	1957		1982	British academic and translator	1930-2003
1930	Gheorghe Mihăilă	1957	1957	2000	Romanian linguist and philologist	1930-2011
1930	Wilferd Madelung	1957	1957	1998	German-American author and scholar of Islamic history	
1930	Shōichi Watanabe	1958	1958	2006	Japanese-British linguist and one of Japan's foremost cultural critics	1930-2017
1930	F. Landa Jocano	1958	1965	1995	Philipino anthropologist, educator, writer and translating the Hinilawod, a Western Visayan folk epic	1930-2013
1930	Aharon Dolgopolsky	1958	1958	2005	Russian-Israeli linguist and one of the modern founders of comparative Nostratic linguistics	1930-2012
1930	Malcolm Parkes	1958		1997	British English paleographer, notable for his contributions to the scholarship of medieval manuscripts	1930-2013
1930	Marija Makarovič	1958		1997 w	Slovenian ethnologist	
1930	Pierre Bourdieu	1958	No	2001	French sociologist, anthropologist, philosopher and public intellectual	1930-2002
1930	Felicia Harben Trager	1959	1968	1972 w	American linguist, President of American Indian linguistics	1930-1972
1930	Aleksandar Mladenović	1959	1963	1995	Serbian linguist, member of the Serbian Academy of Arts and Sciences and an associate of Matica srpska	1930-2010
1930	Ayyappa Paniker	1959	1959	1990	Indian influential Malayalam poet, literary critic, and an academic and a scholar in modern and post-modern literary theories as well as ancient Indian aesthetics and literary traditions.	1930-2006

1930	Ruth Cardoso	1959	1972	1994 w	Brazilian anthropologist and a former member of the Faculty of Philosophy, Letters and Human Sciences	1930-2008
1930	Gerald Berreman	1959	1959	2001	American anthropologist and ethnographer who was known for his theory on the caste system in India, as well as his contributions to the ethical practice of anthropology itself	1930-2013
1930	Dwight B. Heath	1959	1959	2013	American Research Professor of Anthropology	
1930	W. Geoffrey Arnott	1959	1960	1991	British Hellenist who studied comic and other forms of poetry, as well as birds in the ancient world	1930-2010
1930	Doris Bartholomew	1960	1965	2003 w	American anthropologist and linguist (lexicography, historical and descriptive linguistics for indigenous languages in Mexico)	
1930	Robert E. Lee Chadwick	1960	1974	2000	American anthropologist and archeologist, primarily known for his contributions to the Handbook of Middle American Indians	1930-2014
1930	Georges Charachidzé	1960	1968	1998	French scholar of the Caucasian cultures	1930-2010
1930	Hans Vermeer	1961	1962	1992	German linguist and translation scholar	1930-2010
1930	William Alexander Stewart	1961		2002	American linguist (creoles, sociolinguistics)	1930-2002
1930	Laura Nader	1961	1961	2015 w	American anthropologist	
1930	Johanna Narten	1961	1961	2000 w	German Indo-Europeanist and linguist who discovered the reconstructed morphological category in Proto-Indo-European now known as the Narten present	1930-2019
1930	Anson Rainey	1962	1962	2002	American Professor Emeritus of Ancient Near Eastern Cultures and Semitic Linguistics at Tel Aviv University	1930-2011
1930	Cho-yun Hsu	1962	1962	1998	Chinese-American historian	
1930	Maria Luisa Altieri Biagi	1963	No	2002 w	Italian linguistics, a scholar of grammar and history of Italian	1930-2017
1930	Sol Steinmetz	1963		1995	Hungarian-American linguistics and lexicography expert (etymologies, definitions and uncovered earliest recorded usages of words in English and Yiddish)	1930-2010
1930	Zagorka Golubović	1963		1996 w	Serbian philosopher, anthropologist and sociologist	1930-2019
1930	David Simmons	1963		1989	New Zealand ethnologist, historian and author	1930-2015
1930	Karsten Friis Johansen	1964	1964	1998	Danish philosopher and classical philologist	1930-2010
1930	Ghulam Ali Allana	1964	1971	1995	Pakistani writer, critic and linguist	

1930	Saksri Yamnadda	1964	1971	1994	Thai expert in the Thai language, literature and poetry, and taught Thai language, as well as Pali and Sanskrit, as a professor at the Faculty of Arts	
1930	Alfredo Torero	1964	1965	2004	Peruvian anthropologist and linguist	1930-2004
1930	Gananath Obeyesekere	1964	1964	2000	Sri Lankan Professor of Anthropology	
1930	Sue Atkins	1965		2011 w	British lexicographer, pioneered the creation of bilingual dictionaries from corpus data	
1930	Felipe Landa Jocano	1965	1965	1999	Philipino anthropologist, educator, and author known for his significant body of work within the field of Philippine Anthropology	1930-2013
1930	Mehrdād Bahār	1966	1966	1994	Iranian Iranist, linguist, mythologist and Persian historian	1930-1994
1930	Audrey Smedley	1967	1967	2002 w	American social anthropologist and Professor Emeritus at Virginia Commonwealth University in anthropology and African-American studies	
1930	Clara Passafari	1967	1975	1986 w	Argentinean ethnologist, anthropologist, writer and poet	1930-1994
1930	Joann Kealiinohomoku	1967	1976	1987 w	American anthropologist and educator, co-founder of the dance research organization Cross-Cultural Dance Resources	1930-2015
1930	Takie Sugiyama Lebra	1967	1967	1996 w	Japanese anthropologist and professor	1930-2017
1930	Henri J. M. Claessen	1970	1970	1994	Dutch cultural anthropologist specialized in the early state	
1930	Mark Peattie	1973	1973	1995	American academic and Japanologist	
1930	Janet Esser	1975	1978	2003 w	American Professor of art history emerita (Art and Latin American Studies)	
1931	David Bevington	1952	1959	2006	American literary scholar	1931-2019
1931	Richard Rorty	1953	1956	2005	American linguistic philosopher (history of philosophy, contemporary analytic philosophy and comparative literature)	1931-2007
1931	Tomas Tranströmer	1954	1956	1990	Swedish poet, psychologist and translator	1931-2015
1931	Roger Shuy	1954	1962	1998	American linguist (sociolinguistics and forensic linguistics)	
1931	Walter Burkert	1955	1955	1996	German scholar of Greek mythology and cult	1931-2015
1931	Michel Izard	1955	1955	1998	French anthropologist and ethnologist	1931-2012

1931	Barbara Kiefer Lewalski	1956	1956	2010 w	American academic, an authority on Renaissance literature particularly known for her work on John Milton	1931-2018
1931	Andrew P. Vayda	1956	1956	2002	American Distinguished Professor Emeritus of Anthropology and Ecology at Rutgers University	
1931	Hugh M. Stimson	1957	1959	2006	American sinologist and linguist (poetry of the Tang Dynasty (618–907))	1931-2011
1931	Fernando O. Assunção	1957		2006	Uruguayan historian, anthropologist, scholar, historian, and writer	1931-2006
1931	Jean La Fontaine	1957	1957	1983 w	British anthropologist	
1931	Коцюбинська Михайлина	1958	1958	2011 w	Ukrainian linguist	1931-2011
1931	Elizabeth French	1958		1990 w	British director of the British School at Athens and an authority in Mycenaean archaeology, especially pottery and terracotta figurines	
1931	Roy Goodwin D'Andrade	1958	1962	2003	American one of the founders of cognitive anthropology	1931-2016
1931	Hans Staub	1958	1958	1989	Swiss Romanist, comparator, literary scholar and translator	
1931	Bernhard Böschenstein	1958	1958	1998	Swiss Literary scholar	1931-2019
1931	Русанівський ВМ	1959	1959	2007	Soviet-Ukrainian linguist	1931-2007
1931	Grover Krantz	1959	1971	1998	American anthropologist and cryptozoologist; he was one of few scientists not only to research Bigfoot, but also to express his belief in the animal's existence	1931-2002
1931	Edward W. Tayler	1960	1960	1999	American literary scholar	1931-2018
1931	Matthew J. Bruccoli	1960	1960	2005	American Professor of English	1931-2008
1931	Valentí Fàbrega	1960	1972	1996	German Catalan Philologist and Theologian	
1931	Edward Stephan Klima	1961	1965	2008	American linguist (sign languages)	1931-2008
1931	Sorin Stati	1961	1967	1997	Romanian linguist	1931-2008
1931	Nils Hasselmo	1961	1961	1997	American linguist, the thirteenth president of the University of Minnesota	1931-2019
1931	Abdul Haq Ansari	1961	1962	1995	Indian Islamic scholar	
1931	Dora Sakayan	1961	1961	2000 w	Armenian Professor of German Studies	
1931	Michel Cartry	1962		1991	French Africanist and anthropologist of religion	1931-2008
1931	Dong Tichen	1962		1966	Chinese anthropologist and educator, pioneer in physical anthropology in China	1931-1966
1931	Michael M. Cernea	1962	1962	2003	Romanian-American sociologist and anthropologist	

1931	Ursula Bellugi	1963	1967	2018	German Director of the Laboratory for Cognitive Neuroscience	
1931	Bertalan Andrásfalvy	1963	1971	2001	Hungarian ethnographer and politician, Minister of Education (1990-1993)	
1931	Lester Hiatt	1963	1963	1991	Australian scholar of Australian Aboriginal societies who promoted Australian Aboriginal studies within both the academic world	1931-2008
1931	Margaret M. McGowan	1963	1963	1998 w	British dance historian and historian of early modern France	
1931	E. Thomas Lawson	1963	1963	2004	British honorary professor at the Institute of Cognition and Culture	
1931	Julian C. Boyd	1964	1965	1994	American linguist	1931-2005
1931	Ruqaiya Hasan	1964	1964	1994 w	Indian-Australian linguist (systemic functional grammar, sociolinguistics, applied linguistics)	1931-2015
1931	H. Paul Varley	1964	1964	2004	American academic, historian, author, and Japanologist	1931-2015
1931	Jacinto Quirarte	1964	1964	1999	American art historian, professor, scholar and writer who was instrumental in documenting and promoting Latino and Chicano art in the United States	1931-2012
1931	Bo Almqvist	1965	1965	1994	Swedish linguist, writer and folklorist	1931-2013
1931	Maria Bonghi Jovino	1965		2011 w	Italian Professor of Etruscology and Italic Archaeology at the University of Milan	
1931	Owen Lynch	1966	1966	2003	American anthropologist who specialised in the people of India, with particular interest in those now referred to as dalits, who were previously known as untouchables	1931-2013
1931	Gerhard J. Bellinger	1967	1967	1996	German theologian, university professor of the New Testament, the history of Christianity, and the history of religions	
1931	Naseeb Shaheen	1969	1969	2009	American scholar who specialized in Biblical allusions in the work of Shakespeare	1931-2009
1931	Li Yih-yuan	1970		1999	Taiwanese anthropologist	
1931	Christopher Boehm	1972	1972	2010	American cultural anthropologist with a subspecialty in primatology, who researches conflict resolution, altruism, moral origins, and feuding and warfare	

1931	Faina Petryakova	1974	1974	2002 w	Ukrainian distinguished professor of the Lviv Academy of Arts, a recognized figure in the field of ethnography in Ukraine	
1931	Carlos Navarrete Cáceres	1976	1976	2005	Guatemalan anthropologist and writer	
1932	Theodore Ziolkowski	1952	1957	2001	American scholar in the fields of German studies and comparative literature	
1932	Tullio De Mauro	1954		2004	Italian linguist (Minister Edu (2000-2001))	1932-2017
1932	Roger Sale	1954		1999	American literary critic and author	1932-2017
1932	Jaan Puhvel	1955	1959	1989	Estonian-American Indo-Europeanist	
1932	Roger Green	1956	1961	1992	American-New Zealand linguistic archaeologist	1932-2009
1932	Gualtiero Calboli	1957		2001	Italian classicist and linguist	
1932	Harold Toliver	1958	1961	1999	American literary critic, theorist and writer	
1932	Vitaly Shevoroshkin	1958		1995	Georgian-American linguist of Russian origin (study of ancient Mediterranean languages)	
1932	Robert T. Harms	1958	1960	2006	American linguist (grammar of Estonian and phonological theory)	1932-2016
1932	Max Pfister	1958	1958	1999	Swiss Romance studies scholar and linguist	1932-2017
1932	Abul Khair Kashfi	1958	1971	1994	Pakistani author, researcher, critic, linguist and scholar of Urdu literature and linguistics	1932-2008
1932	Donald Kagan	1958	1958	2013	Lithuanian-American historian and classicist	
1932	John Searle	1959	1959	2014	American philosopher (philosophy of language, philosophy of mind, and social philosophy)	
1932	Patty Jo Watson	1959	1959	2004 w	American archaeologist renowned for her work on Pre-Columbian Native Americans	
1932	Julio Cotler	1959	1959	1993	Peruvian anthropologist, sociologist and political scientist	1932-2019
1932	Lauri Honko	1959	1959	1990	Finnish professor of folklore studies and comparative religion	1932-2002
1932	Hashimoto Mantarō	1960	1965	1987	Japanese sinologist	1932-1987
1932	Jerrold Katz	1960	1960	2002	American philosopher and linguist	1932-2002
1932	Yevgeny Kychanov	1960	1960	2003	Russian orientalist, an expert on the Tangut people and their mediaeval Xi Xia Empire	1932-2013
1932	Elli-Kajja Kõngäs-Maranda	1960	1963	1982 w	Canadian internationally renowned anthropologist and feminist folklorist	1932-1982

1932	Sylvia M. Broadbent	1960	1960	1992 w	British-American anthropologist and professor, specializing in Amerindian peoples	1932-2015
1932	Tim Asch	1961	No	1994	American anthropologist, photographer, and ethnographic filmmaker	1932-1994
1932	Getatchew Haile	1962	1962		Ethiopian-American philologist (Ge'ez language alive today)	
1932	Andreas Bjørkum	1962	1962	2002	Norwegian philologist who specialized in dialectology	1932-2014
1932	Carmen Castillo García	1962	1962	2002	Spanish Professor Emeritus of Classical Philology	
1932	Wick R. Miller	1962	1965	1994	American linguist	1932-1994
1932	Reina Torres de Araúz	1962	1963	1982 w	Panamanian prominent anthropologist, ethnographer and professor	1932-1982
1932	Margarita Nolasco Armas	1962		2000 w	Mexican ethnologist and anthropologist	1932-2008
1932	Joyce Blau	1963		2007 w	French linguist, specialist in Kurdish language and literature	
1932	Cecilia Lindqvist	1963	No	2007 w	Swedish Sinologist	
1932	Richard T. Antoun	1963	1963	1999	American anthropologist who specialized in Islamic and Middle Eastern studies	1932-2009
1932	Roland Hagenbüchle	1964	1964	1996	Swiss scholar for American Studies and cultural philosopher	1932-2008
1932	Donald Gutierrez	1964	1964	1994	American writer and professor emeritus of English literature	1932-2013
1932	Harry J. Cargas	1964	1971	1998	American scholar, author, and teacher best known for his writing and research on the Holocaust, Jewish-Catholic relations, and American literature	1932-1998
1932	Judith Becker	1964	1972	2008 w	American academic (musical and religious cultures of South and Southeast Asia, the Islamic world and the Americas) and educator	
1932	John Lyons	1964		2000	British linguist, working on semantics	1932-2020
1932	Barbara Herrnstein Smith	1965	1965	2012 w	American literary critic and theorist	
1932	Asen Chilingirov	1965	1971	1998	Bulgarian art historian and culturologist	
1932	Alton L. Becker	1965	1968	1986	American linguist (Burmese grammar and Malaysian, Javanese and Kawi)	1932-2011
1932	Shmuel Moreh	1965	1965	1999	Iragi-Israeli professor of Arabic Language and Literature	1932-2017
1932	Talal Asad	1966	1968	2007	Saudi Arabian-American cultural anthropologist	

1932	Henri Meschonnic	1967		2002	French poet, linguist, essayist and translator	1932-2009
1932	Yadollah Samareh	1968	1968	2004	Iranian linguist	1932-2019
1932	Egil Törnqvist	1968	1968	1997	Swedish Professor Emeritus of Scandinavian Studies at the University of Amsterdam and an academic literary critic	1932-2015
1932	Barbara Harrell-Bond	1969		1996 w	British-American social scientist in the field of refugee studies	1932-2018
1932	Régis Boyer	1970	1972	2001	French literary scholar, historian and translator, specialised on Nordic literature and the Viking Age	
1932	Larissa Adler Lomnitz	1971	1974	2010 w	Chilean-Mexican French-born social anthropologist, researcher, professor, and academic	
1932	George Chaloupka	1973		1998	Czech-Australian expert on Indigenous Australian rock art	
1932	Carol Laderman	1975		2010 w	American groundbreaking medical anthropologist, specializing in the study of pregnancy and childbirth practices, shamanism, and Southeast Asian cultures	
1932	Marc Fumaroli	1976	1976	2002	French historian and essayist	
1932	Ann Jannetta	1983	1983	2006 w	American academic, historian, author, Japanologist and Professor of History Emerita	
1932	Freda Ahenakew	1985	No	1996 w	Canadian author and academic of Cree descent	1932-2011
1933	Jerzy Kolendo	1952	1960	2003	Polish historian and archaeologist who specialized in the history of ancient Rome	1933-2014
1933	Seyyed Hossein Nasr	1952	1958	2011	Iranian Professor of Islamic Studies	
1933	Martin Puhvel	1955	1958	1998	Estonian-Canadian literature researcher (old and medieval English literature)	1933-2016
1933	Gail M. Kelly	1955	1959	2000 w	American anthropologist	1933-2005
1933	Marvin Dale Kinkade	1956	1963	1998	American linguist (Salishan languages)	1933-2004
1933	Anton Popovič	1956	1956	1984	Slovak translation scientist and text theoretician	1933-1984
1933	John Gardner	1956	1958	1982	American novelist, essayist, literary critic and university professor	1933-1982
1933	Michael M. Ames	1956	1961	1997	Canadian academic and Professor of Anthropology	1933-2006
1933	Michael Stokes	1956		1993	British Professor of Greek	1933-2012
1933	R. E. A. Palmer	1956	1956	2006	American historian and a leading figure in the study of archaic Rome	1933-2006

1933 Daniel Seltzer	1957	1957	1980	American professor of English at Princeton University, an actor and a Shakespearean scholar	1933-1980
1933 Sophie Coe	1957	1964	1994 w	American anthropologist, food historian and author, primarily known for her work on the history of chocolate	1933-1994
1933 Alan T. Davies	1957	1966	1998	Canadian Christian minister and emeritus professor of religion	
1933 Prof. Henry Guntur Tarigan	1958	1975	1991	Indonesian linguist	
1933 Irmengard Rauch	1958	1963	2018 w	American linguist and semiotician.	
1933 Melvin Ember	1958	1958	1999	American cultural anthropologist and cross-cultural researcher with wide-ranging interests who combined an active research career with writing for nonprofessionals	1933-2009
1933 Mervyn C. Alleyne	1959	1959	2007	Trinidadian sociolinguist, creolist and dialectologist (creole languages of the Caribbean)	1933-2016
1933 Alexander Welsh	1959	1961	2006	American philologist	1933-2018
1933 Calvert Watkins	1959	1959	2003	American linguist and philologist	1933-2013
1933 Ben Finney	1959	1966	2000	American anthropologist known for his expertise in the history and the cultural and social anthropology of surfing, Polynesian navigation, and canoe sailing, as well as in the cultural and social anthropology of human space colonization	1933-2017
1933 Michael C. J. Putnam	1959	1959	2008	American classicist specializing in Latin literature, but has also studied literature written in many other languages	
1933 Georg Heike	1960	1960	1998	German phonetician, linguist, musician and composer	
1933 Trevor H. Howard-Hill	1960	1960	1999	New Zealand scholar of English literature, leading figure in the field of bibliography and book history	1933-2011
1933 Pierre L. van den Berghe	1960	1960	2012	Belgian professor emeritus of sociology and anthropology	1933-2019
1933 Michael Maccoby	1960	1960	2000	American psychoanalyst and anthropologist globally recognized as an expert on leadership for his research, writing and projects to improve organizations and work	

1933	Raymond D. Fogelson	1960	1962	2011	American anthropologist, a founder of the subdiscipline of ethnohistory	1933-2020
1933	Wallace Kirsop	1960	1960	1998	Australian scholar in French studies and in book trade history	
1933	Susumu Kuno	1961	1964	1999	Japanese linguist and author	
1933	Klaus Klostermaier	1961	1961	2004	German-Canadian scholar on Hinduism and Indian history and culture	
1933	Німчук ВВ	1962	1962	2017	Soviet-Ukrainian linguist	1933-2017
1933	Yamuna Kachru	1962	1962	1999 w	Indian-American Professor Emerita of Linguistics	1933-2013
1933	Sharafbonu Pulodova	1962	1962	2000 w	Tajikistani philologist, Indologist, and Orientalist	
1933	Lucien Sebag	1963		1965	French Marxist anthropologist (trying to reconcile structuralism and marxism)	1933-1965
1933	Arthur Asa Berger	1965	1965	1998	American professor emeritus at the Department of Broadcast and Electronic Communication Arts	
1933	John McHardy Sinclair	1965	1967	2000	British Professor of Modern English Language	1933-2007
1933	Ruth A. Berman	1965	1933	2003 w	Israeli linguist	
1933	Betty Meehan	1965		1995 w	Australian archaeologist and anthropologist who has worked extensively with Aboriginal people in Arnhem Land, Northern Territory	
1933	C. Scott Littleton	1965	1965	2002	American anthropologist and academic	1933-2010
1933	Froma Zeitlin	1965	1970	2005	American Classics scholar	
1933	Bernard G. Weiss	1966	1966	1998	American professor of languages and literature	1933-2018
1933	Norma Diamond	1966	1966	1996 w	American anthropologist who specialized in the study of Chinese society, especially in Taiwan, and women's studies	1933-2011
1933	Heinrich von Stietencron	1966	1966	1998	German Professor and the Director of the Institute of Indology and Comparative Religion	1933-2018
1933	Denise Schmandt-Besserat	1967		2004 w	French-American professor emerita of Art and Middle Eastern Studies	
1933	Ladislav Holý	1967		1996	Czech anthropologist and Africanist of the British school of social anthropology	1933-1997
1933	Robert S. Ellwood	1967	1967	1997	American academic, author and expert on world religions	
1933	Françoise Héritier	1968	1990	1999 w	French nthropologist, ethnologist, and feminist	1933-2017
1933	Moira Roth	1968	1974	2000 w	British-American feminist art historian and art critic	

1933	Alice McLerran	1969	1969	2000 w	American anthropologist and author	1933-2019
1933	John H. Schutz	1969		1998	American Emeritus Professor of Religious Studies	1933-2015
1933	Janet Burstein	1970	1975	2004 w	American emerita professor of english literature	
1933	Jasleen Dhamija	1970		1991 w	Indian veteran Indian textile art historian, crafts expert and former UN worker	
1933	David Tod Roy	1971		1999	American sinologist and scholar of Chinese literature, Professor of East Asian Languages and Civilizations	
1933	Gerald Mars	1972	1972	2008	British social anthropologist who works across disciplines to understand the nature and problems of modern industrial society	
1933	Vivian Garrison	1972	1972	1993 w	American applied medical anthropologist who researched mental health care among low-income, minority, and migrant communities in the New York metropolitan area	
1933	Richard Beaudesne	1974	1975	1999	Canadian Professor Emeritus of Religious Studies	
1933	Annette Weiner	1976	1976	1997 w	American anthropologist	
1934	Herbert S. Lewis	1954	1963	1998	American Professor Emeritus of Anthropology	
1934	Kenneth L. Hale	1955	1959	1999	American linguist	1934-2001
1934	Renzo Pi Hugarte	1955	1968	1997	Uruguayan scholar, anthropologist, professor, historian and writer, " founding fathers " of anthropology in Uruguay	1934-2012
1934	Vincenzo Di Benedetto	1955		2006	Italian classical philologist	1934-2013
1934	Michael E. Krauss	1956	1959	2000	American linguist, founder and long-time head of the Alaska Native Language Center	1934-2019
1934	Jørgen Rischel	1957	1974	1998	Danish linguist	
1934	Amalia Signorelli	1957		2004	Italian classicist and linguist	1934-2017
1934	Philip Gough	1958	1961	2004	American the Regents Professor Emeritus of Psychology (Psycholinguistics, Reading, Linguistics)	
1934	Irving Malin	1958	1958	1996	American literary critic	1934-2014
1934	Alice Beck Kehoe	1958	1964	2000 w	American feminist anthropologist and archaeologist	
1934	Jerzy Linderski	1958	1960	2004	Polish contemporary scholar of ancient history and Roman religion and law	

1934 Philip Lieberman	1959	1966	2012	American cognitive scientist (evolution of language, relationship between the evolution of the vocal tract, the human brain, and the evolution of speech, cognition and language)	
1934 Harris Winitz	1959	1959	2013	American professor in psycholinguistics, phonetics, acoustic phonetics, and language pathology and conducted research in second language learning	
1934 Nicholas Millet	1959	1969	2004	American Egyptologist affiliated with the Royal Ontario Museum	1934-2004
1934 Sige-Yuki Kuroda	1960	1965	1994	Japanese Research Professor of Linguistics	1934-2009
1934 Ineke van Wetering	1960		2010 w	Dutch anthropologist and Surinamist	1934-2011
1934 Cesare Questa	1960		2001	Italian classicist particularly known for his studies of the metres of the Roman playwrights Plautus and Terence	
					1934-2016
1934 Peter Horn	1961	1970	2014	Czech-South African poet (Professor of German Literature)	1934-2019
1934 Jarle Bondevik	1961	1961	1999	Norwegian philologist	1934-2016
1934 George Hillocks Jr.	1961	1961	2003	American professor of English Language and Literature	
					1934-2014
1934 Irvén DeVore	1961	1962	2004	American anthropologist and evolutionary biologist, and Curator of Primatology at Harvard University's Peabody Museum of Archaeology and Ethnology	1934-2014
1934 Elisabeth Endres	1961	1961	2000 w	German Germanist, historian, literary critic and journalist	
					1934-2000
1934 Lionel Bender	1962	1968	1996	American linguist	1934-2008
1934 Eva Verbitsky Hunt	1962	1962	1980 w	Argentinean cultural anthropologist, academic and writer	
					1934-1980
1934 Robin Fox	1962	1978	1997	British Anglo-American anthropologist who has written on the topics of incest avoidance, marriage systems, human and primate kinship systems, evolutionary anthropology, sociology and the history of ideas in the social sciences	
1934 Pierre Clastres	1962		1977	French anthropologist and ethnologist	1934-1977
1934 Alan Dundes	1962	1962	2005	American folklorist	1934-2005
1934 Antoine Faivre	1962		2002	French scholar of Western esotericism	

1934 Paul Kay	1963	1963	1995	American emeritus professor of linguistics and colors	
1934 Åse-Marie Nesse	1963	1963	2000 w	Norwegian philologist, translator and poet	1934-2001
1934 Mel Bradford	1963		1993	American conservative political commentator and professor of literature	1934-1993
1934 Carolyn See	1963	1963	2014 w	American professor emerita of English and author	1934-2016
1934 John Okell	1963		1999	British linguist notable for his expertise in the field of Burma studies	
1934 Anne Elizabeth Pennington	1964	1964	1981 w	British philologist specialising in Slavic studies	1934-1981
1934 Emiko Ohnuki-Tierney	1964	1968	2009 w	Japanese-American noted anthropologist and the William F. Vilas Professor of Anthropology	
1934 Maurice Godelier	1964		2001	French anthropologist, one of the earliest advocates of Marxism's incorporation into anthropology	
1934 Aleksandras Vanagas	1965	1965	1995	Lithuanian linguist, professor, researcher of onomastics	1934-1995
1934 Arlene Croce	1965		1998 w	American dance critic	
1934 Alan Isler	1965	1967	1995	American novelist and professor	1934-2010
1934 Joseph Fletcher	1965	1965	1984	American historian of China and Central Asia and a professor in the East Asian Languages and Civilizations Department	1934-1984
1934 Verjine Svazlian	1965	1965	2004 w	Armenian ethnographer and folklorist, historian, Genocide Scholar	
1934 Peter Rivière	1965	1965	2001	British social anthropologist	
1934 John Chowning	1966	1966	1996	American composer, musician, discoverer, and professor	
1934 Carlota Smith	1966	1967	1991 w	American linguist	1934-2007
1934 Giovanni Pettinato	1966	1968	2010	Italian paleographer of writings from the ancient Near East, specializing in the Eblaite language	1934-2011
1934 Jeanne Favret-Saada	1966		1997 w	French ethnologist	
1934 Carol Myers-Scotton	1967	1967	2003 w	American linguist (language contact)	
1934 Maurice Gross	1967	1967	2001	French linguist and scholar of Romance languages, computational scientist	1934-2001
1934 Zeus A. Salazar	1968	1968	2000	Philipino historian, anthropologist, and philosopher of history, " Father of New Philippine Historiography "	
1934 Donald Brown	1968	1969	1994	American professor of anthropology (emeritus)	

1934	Jerrold Sadock	1969	1969	2009	American the Glen A. Lloyd Distinguished Service Professor in Linguistics	1934-2008
1934	Amnon Netzer	1969	1969	2004	Iranian-Israeli historian, researcher, professor and journalist	
1934	Geoffrey Thorndike Martin	1969	1969	1993	British egyptologist, the Edwards Professor of Egyptian Archaeology and Philology	
1934	Víctor García de la Concha	1970	1970	2017	Spanish secularized priest and philologist	
1934	AllahDad Bohyo	1970	1977	1994	Pakistani writer, educationist, scholar, linguist and poet	
1934	Robert W. Thomson	1970	1977	2001	British the Calouste Gulbenkian Professor of Armenian Studies at Oxford University	
1934	Don Lee Fred Nilsen	1971	1971	2005	American linguist and humor scholar	
1934	Patricia Barchas	1971	1971	1993 w	American scholar committed to the study of the interaction of social behavior and physiological processes (pioneer in the study of brain electrical activity and hormonal function in social processes, such as the development of status hierarchies in small social groups)	
1934	Fanny Colonna	1971		1993 w	French-Algerian sociologist and anthropologist	
1934	Elaine Ostrach Chaika	1972	1972	2008 w	American professor emeritus of Linguistics and English at Providence College	
1934	Nurhan Atasoy	1972	1972	1999 w	Turkish art historian	
1934	LaVerne Jeanne	1974	1978	2000 w	American anthropologist and linguist	
1934	Gong Hwang-cherng	1975	1975	2004	Taiwanese Chinese linguist who specialized in Sino-Tibetan comparative linguistics and the phonetic reconstruction of Tangut and Old Chinese	
1934	Ruth Cernea	1975	1982	2002 w	American cultural anthropologist, who dedicated virtually all her field research and writings to the analysis of Jewish culture and symbols, in various settings	
1934	Lilly Wong Fillmore	1976	1976	2004 w	American linguist	
1934	Mohammad Reza Bateni	1976		2010	Iranian linguist	
1934	Gillian Cowlishaw	1979	1979	2005 w	New Zealand-Australian anthropologist who researches Aboriginal Australian culture and people	

1934 Oscar Kawagley

1983

1994

2011

American Yup'ik (Alaska Native) anthropologist, teacher
and actor

1934-2011